

SUBJECTIVE SIGNS OF BULLYING IN A GROUP OF PERSONS

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Annotation: The article analyzes the crime of hooliganism committed by a group of people and the subjective signs of these crimes.

Key words: crime, subject of crime, criminal code, hooliganism, criminal responsibility, criminal , etc.

The necessary subjective features of the crime are the subject and the subjective party. According to the generally recognized approach , the subject of the crime is a sane person who has committed a crime, has reached the age of criminal responsibility, and in some cases has certain characteristics specified in the relevant norm of the Special Part of the Criminal Code.

Based on the above, we can conclude that the subject of bullying is a sane person who has reached the age of 16 or 14 (in aggravated cases).

the correct classification of the crime , the subject of the crime is of great importance. As AN Trainin rightly stated: "...where there is no person guilty of a crime, there can be no question about the presence or absence of a crime..." 1. Therefore, the correct identification of the signs of the subject of the crime is the key to the objective qualification of the crime.

According to BAKurinov, the signs of a criminal subject "can be conditionally divided into two groups : criminological features and signs of a criminal-legal nature" 2. In particular, criminological characteristics are the criminal's moral-political image, his psychological and spiritual characteristics. The signs of the second group "include only the signs of the subject of the crime that are important for solving the issue of bringing a person to criminal responsibility

1Traynin A.N. Obshchee uchenie o sostave prestupleniya. M.: Gosyurizdat, 1957. S. 191.

2Kurinov B.A. Nauchnye osnovy kvalificatsii prestupleniya. M., 1984. P.93.

." The signs of the second group 3include the characteristics of the subject of the crime given in Article 17 of the Criminal Code: natural person; age; sanity.

In relation to bullying, we will consider each of these signs separately.

The first sign does not cause any difficulties, because according to Article 17 of the Criminal Code, the subject of a crime, in particular, bullying, can only be a natural person . According to the criminal law, legal entities cannot be the subject of a crime.

The most controversial thing in the science of criminal law is the second indicator of the subject of bullying - age.

Age plays an important role in characterizing the perpetrators of bullying. Taking into account the age, one can assess the level of socialization of a person, that is, a person's certain social status, interests, needs, life attitude and value orientations.

According to the opinion of most scientists , the possibility of bringing criminal responsibility from the age of at least 14 is related to the emergence of the offender's ability to understand the social danger of certain actions and their social importance 4. In addition, some authors even conclude that lowering the lower age limits of criminal responsibility for certain crimes to 12-13 years takes into account the existing criminogenic situation, the practice of foreign legislation in this regard, and the age characteristics of teenagers.

As a sign of a criminal subject, the age of a person is determined by the number of years he has lived. In accordance with Article 17 of the Criminal Code, the subject of the crime referred to in Article 277, Part 1 of the Criminal Code is 16 years old, and the subject of the crimes referred to in Article 277, Parts 2 and 3 of the Criminal Code is a 14-year-old sane individual.

What is the reason for such age-based criminal liability for "simple" bullying and aggravated bullying?

The need to establish criminal liability from the age of 14 for committing the crime provided for in Article 277, Part 1 of the Criminal Code is evidenced by many facts related to "ordinary" hooliganism committed by teenagers under the age of 16.

3Ugolovnoe pravo Rossiyskoy Federatsii. Obshchaya chast: Uchebnik dlya vuzov / P od ed. A.I. Raroga, A.S. Samoilova. M.: Vysshee obrazovanie, 2005. P.213.

4Kurinov B.A. Nauchnye osnovy qualificatsii prestupleniya. M., 1984. P.93.

However, the legislator does not take into account the current reality. Nor does it take into account that bullying has historically been considered a "juvenile" crime, even though it has long been committed primarily by homeless youth. It's no coincidence that even in thieves' jargon, the word "bastard" has several meanings: thug, novice criminal 5.

It should be noted that the issue of the minimum age of criminal responsibility is very controversial not only in criminal law and criminology, but also in pedagogy, psychology, and medicine. At present, there are many opinions about lowering the age of criminal responsibility, with authors proposing various "age minimums" — 12 and even 11 years.

It should be taken into account that these indicators do not reflect the actual number of cases of hooliganism committed by minors due to the sufficiently public and latent nature of this crime. The legislator's wrong approach to solving this issue indicates that mistakes were made in the Criminal Code. Based on the above, in our opinion, setting the age limit of criminal responsibility for hooliganism at 16 years is not fully social and scientific, it does not meet the needs of fighting crime and the current criminogenic situation.

It is worth noting once again that today the age limit of criminal responsibility set by the legislator is negatively evaluated by scientists. Some psychologists, based on the features of the level of intellectual, voluntary, personal development of minors, agree with the opinion of the legislator and believe that it is correct to set the age limits for criminal responsibility at 14 and 16 years, at the same time, for a number of the age of criminal responsibility for crimes may be reduced.

In general, the analysis makes it possible to emphasize that the characteristics of hooliganism are to a certain extent related to the person who commits the crime belonging to a certain age group. At the same time, the most criminogenically active are persons under the age of 30 . Particular attention should be paid to the characteristics of adolescence and early youth, because these characteristics play a very important role in determining the age criteria of criminal responsibility 6.

5Bykov V. Russkaya Fenya . Slovar sovremennogo interjargona asotsialnykh elementov. Smolensk: TRUST-IMAKOM, 1993. P.22.; Borovykh L.V. Problemy age and mechanism of criminal-law regulation: autoref. dne. . . and _ walk science Yekaterinburg, 1993. P.13; Baybarin A.A. K voprosu o minimalnoy vozrastnoy granitse nastupleniya ogolovnoy otvetstvennosti // Aktualnye problemy rossiyskogo prava. 2008. #1.S.216.

6Ugolovnoe pravo Rossiyskoy Federatsii. Obshchaya chast: Uchebnik dlya vuzov / Podred. A.I. Raroga, A.S. Samoilova. M.: Vysshee obrazovanie, 2005. P.213.

is social immaturity, which occurs due to insufficient mental, intellectual and physical development. The emergence of the idea that he is no longer a child in a teenager (psychologists call this "sense of adulthood") determines his reorientation of childhood values and norms in relation to adults, he asks others to recognize his greatness. begins to need.

Manifestation of personal qualities of a teenager can be in different forms, sometimes they can look antisocial. Bullying committed by teenagers is often expressed as violence against a person. Beating victims is often used by adolescents as a means of self-affirmation or moral concepts (showing their courage, determination, fear of being labeled a coward, and keeping up with their peers. lish, etc.) is carried out for corruption. At the same time, teenagers, as a rule, know the social danger of beating. But due to the underdevelopment of thinking, the lack of stable ideas about moral and spiritual categories, the insufficient level of mental development, "unlike adults, minors do not fully understand the essence of the crime committed and the level of social danger. they cannot understand . "7

In particular, 14-15-year-old teenagers do not always fully understand that by beating a person, the conditions for the normal exercise of rights and obligations by other persons (that is, the maintenance of public order) are disturbed. At the same time, they understand that their behavior violates established norms of behavior and that such behavior is considered illegal in society. It can be said that harming public order as the main object of bullying is recognized by teenagers only in a general sense, but this is sufficient for criminal liability for bullying .

We agree with the authors who believe that the modern criminal policy is aimed at maximum humanization of the measures of impact on the criminal, therefore, it is impossible to reduce the age of criminal responsibility 8. Lowering the age of criminal responsibility for bullying to 13, 12 or even 11 is not appropriate. However, the age limit provided for in part 1 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code should be harmonized with parts 2 and 3 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code . In accordance with part 1 of Article 277 of the Criminal Code, the age of criminal responsibility should be set at 14 years, because setting a different age limit for offenses related to it does not correctly assess the criminogenic situation and the mental capacity of minors.

7Tkachenko V. Otvetstvennost za hooliganstvo // Zakonnost. 2006. #7. P.29 - 31

8Arseneva M.I., Ermakov V.D., Pankratov V.V. Criminological characteristics of age-related parameters of legal responsibility //Nesovershennoletnie: ix age-related characteristics and problems of legal responsibility. M., 1992. P.31.

Now , let's look at the next sign of bullying subject - intelligence .

The concept of sanity in the national criminal legislation is contained in Article 18 of the Criminal Code. Various definitions of this term have been proposed in criminal law and psychiatric theory, but the most successful is Yu.M. Given by Antonyan and SV Borodin. According to them , sanity is a state of mind that indicates a certain development, socialization, age and state of mental health of a person at the time of committing a crime, the ability to understand and control their actions, and in the future, this in relation, criminal responsibility means liability and punishment 9.

Awareness of the public danger of bullying is closely related to sanity, that is, the subject's ability to understand and control his actions. Incomplete formation of the adolescent nervous system, excitability, impressionability, etc., can slightly narrow the role of the mind in exercising control over its own behavior.

deviations of minors (so-called "borderline cases") or due to mental retardation lead to the fact that they cannot fully understand the meaning of their actions and cannot control them. In this, we face the problem of limited sanity of minors 10.

The ability to understand the factual aspect of one's actions, their social significance and the ability to consciously control one's actions distinguishes a sane person from an insane person. The performance of any actions by a sane person presupposes that his mind and will participate in them, because such a person is able to objectively evaluate external conditions and, based on their evaluation, choose the optimal behavior options for him.

Based on the concept of insanity defined in Article 18 of the Criminal Code, there are two criteria for determining the state of insanity - medical and legal criteria.

Most of the bullying is done under the influence of alcohol. In accordance with Article 19 of the Criminal Code, persons who have committed a crime in this case shall be held criminally liable on a general basis.

Based on the above, the following conclusions can be drawn: the subject of bullying is a sane individual who has reached the age of 16 or 14 (who has committed bullying in aggravating and extremely aggravating cases).

9Antonyan Yu.M., Borodin S.V. Addiction and psychological anomaly. M., 1987. S. 123-124.

10Tkachenko V. Otvetstvennost za hooliganstvo // Zakonnost. 2006. #7. P.29 - 31

According to VN Kudryavsev , the subjective side of the crime is the mental activity of the person directly related to the commission of the crime, the reflection of the objective signs of the crime in the mind of the subject (possibility of reflection), the subject's attitude towards it ¹¹. This view is generally accepted in the science of criminal law. A necessary sign of the subjective side of the crime is the presence of guilt — "the mental attitude of the person to the crime he committed."

At the same time, it is emphasized in legal literature that guilt does not exist as a concrete, real event, it is an abstraction, which is common to all elements that make up the subjective side of mental attitude. Crime is manifested in individual real mental events - motive, goal, emotional attitude, decision to choose the means to achieve the goal .

Controversial issues regarding the subjective aspect of bullying have been and still are in the science of criminal law, and their unresolved nature certainly does not affect practice.

The subjective aspect of bullying is unique in that its components are part of some other crimes. Yu.A. As Krasikov rightly said, the norm of the law on bullying requires the disclosure and explanation of the subjective side of this crime.

There are several perspectives on the question of the form of intention as part of the subjective aspect of bullying. AN Ignatov expresses the opinion that hooliganism can be committed with right and wrong intention: "... as a rule, hooliganism is committed with right intention, that is, the subject himself violates public order through his offense realizes that he is committing a socially dangerous act that violates the law and wants to show disrespect to the society. But there can also be ulterior motives . The subject of the hooligan with malicious intent foresees the possibility that his action may violate the public order, contradict the public interests, and deliberately allows disrespect for the society to be ¹²shown . A similar opinion was expressed by some other scientists.

According to LV Serdyuk, bullying can be committed with right or wrong intention in relation to socially dangerous consequences: "...the subject wants certain consequences to occur (for example, as a result of beating). Other negative consequences may not be intended in his

¹¹Rossiyskoe ugolovnoe pravo. Osobennaya chast / P od ed. V.N. Kudryavtseva and A.V. Naumova. M.: Jurist, 1997. S. 228.

¹²Ignatov A. Spornye voprosy qualificatsii hooliganstva // Sovetskaya yustitsiya. 1987. No. 2. S. 14.

criminal actions , but he consciously allows them to occur or is indifferent to their occurrence (for example, violation of the traffic order in the community)" 13.

As we mentioned above, the crime of hooliganism belongs to the category of mixed (formal and material content) crimes, and some of its content does not require the existence of socially dangerous consequences, therefore, it is assumed that the decisive factor for determining intent in formal crimes is the psychological attitude of a person to the act he committed. can be done.

intention in crimes with a formal content includes only a mental attitude towards the action and a certain volitional attitude towards it 14. Based on this rule, the concept of guilt in the form of correct intent in bullying with a formal content can look like this: if a person knows the social danger of his actions, and wants to carry them out, the crime it is recognized as having been committed with the right intention.

It should be noted that in the science of criminal law, there is an opinion that the motive of bullying is always a necessary sign of the subjective side of bullying. In this regard, BS Volkov writes that "this motive cannot be considered as a necessary element of the subjective side of the crime. If there is no motive for bullying, there will be no bullying 15." Most of the experts we surveyed (71%) However, not all researchers agree with this position.

In this regard, serious attention is being paid to the content and essence of bullying motives in recent scientific works. BVVolzhenkin sees the essence of the bully's motive in a rude attitude towards the whole society, opposition to public opinion, moral standards, showing one's superiority, brute force, 16etc.

According to AIKorobeev, when considering the issue of the motives of hooliganism, such motives are the manifestation of extreme egocentrism by the criminal, intolerance of moral

13Serdyuk L.V. Nasilie: kriminologicheskoe i ugolovno-pravovoe investigation. M.: Yurlitinform, 2002. S. 22.

14Krieger G. Opredelenie formy viny // Sovetskaya justice. 1979. No. 20. S. 4

15Volkov B.S. Motive and qualification prespleniy. Kazan, 1968. S. 152

16Volzhenkin B.V., Pitertsev S.K., Shimanovsky V.V. Rassledovanie del o hooliganstve. L., 1979. S.

and legal prohibitions and restrictions existing in society, human dignity through his aggressive actions. is an expression of the desire to reduce the price 17.

According to LA Andreeva, the goal of hooliganism "comes from selfishness associated with lack of respect for human dignity, indifference to public interests, disregard for laws and rules of conduct, and from satisfaction of the criminal's antisocial needs. "based on anger" 18. V. Ya. Kozachenko stated that "the goal of bullying is expressed in the desire to stamp in people's minds the absolute uniqueness of the criminal on a hypertrophic level. At the same time, a bully can control his behavior with not one, but several motives, but in any case this motive prevails 19. According to SVBorodin, the motives of bullying are generally devoid of any need, that is, a person does not want something meaningful 20.

In our opinion, all the above definitions help to understand the psychological and legal nature of the bullying motive. At the same time, they cannot clearly and concisely provide the necessary formulas to create a normative definition of the concept of "bullying motive".

Based on the above opinions of scientists who have considered the problem of bullying motives, studied criminal case materials and examples of court practice, in our opinion, the main link of the motivation of bullying actions is society, others, and the personal value of a certain person. disdain, defying the requirements of public order through one's actions, seeking to display one's personality in an illegal way, showing one's strength, courage, cruelty, mocking a defenseless person, protesting against the state order, is to go against public morals. Consequently, as a result, the motive of bullying manifests itself in committing actions that are part of the objective side of bullying and attack public order. Based on this, in our opinion, it should be recognized that there is a need to formulate the legal concept of "bullying motive".

Motives of hooliganism should definitely be classified as a low motive, because the actions committed as a result of their external manifestation are aimed at harming social relations protected by criminal law and ultimately harming people as members of society .

17Rossiyskoe ugovnoe pravo. Course lecture / P od ed. A.I. Korobeeva. T. III. Vladivostok, 2000. S. 115.

18Andreeva L.A. Qualification ubiystv, sovershennyx pri otyagchayushchix obstayatelstvax. S. 32.

19Ugovnoe pravo. Osobennaya chast: Uchebnik / P od ed. I. Ya. Kozachenko, Z.A. Neznamovoy, G.P. Novoselova. M. - 2009. - S. 390.

20Antonyan Yu.M., Borodin S.V. Addiction and psychological anomaly. M., 1987. S. 123-124

Based on the above, it is necessary to conclude that the motives of bullying are a person's open disrespect for society and generally accepted behavior that ensures public and civil peace, normal working conditions, recreation and living conditions, and normal activities of enterprises and organizations. should be understood as motives expressed in the desire to show disregard for the rules.

When considering the issues of the subjective side of bullying, it should be noted that the actions that are externally similar to bullying, personal enmity, or as a result of the wrong actions of the victims, are qualified by the articles of the Criminal Code that provide for responsibility for crimes against the person. should be done.

